

THE ROLE OF MATRIX RESIN MICRO-SCALE PROPERTIES ON THE AXIAL TENSILE STRENGTH OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

In unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (CFRP) laminates, the distance between fibers can vary several orders of magnitude from submicron to micron length scales. The properties of the matrix at this length scale are not well understood and may deviate from the bulk epoxy properties. In this study, processing methods have been developed to produce high quality epoxy fibers for tensile testing and unidirectional composite samples are tested to establish the correlation between resin properties and CFRP tensile strength.

5 types of epoxy resin systems were prepared and epoxy fiber specimens with diameter in the range of 100-150 μ m were used for tensile test. Macro scale epoxy specimens are tested using ASTM D638 to compare results to the epoxy fiber specimens. Epoxy fiber specimens showed ductile behaviour with a distinct yield stress in all resin systems. In contrast, the macroscopic specimens exhibited brittle failure with failure strains in the 1-5% range. Failure strain of epoxy micro fibers were significantly higher than that of macroscopic specimens with failure strain reaching 65% as maximum in DGEBA sample (about 10 times higher than the macroscopic specimen). In addition, yield stress of the fiber specimens (85-115MPa) were significantly higher compare to maximum stress of macroscopic scale specimens (50-70MPa). These results at more realistic length scales indicate that the tensile properties of epoxy matrices in CFRP differ significantly from the bulk.

Tensile testing of unidirectional CFRP composed of each epoxy resin systems is carried out to understand the effect of matrix resin micro-scale properties on CFRP tensile properties. The CFRP composed of highest yield stress resin showed highest tensile strength and composed of highest failure strain resin exhibited second highest strength. The results imply that high yield stress matrices reduced stress recovery length and high failure strain matrices reduced stress concentration on adjacent intact fibers after fiber breakage, both effect allowing for the measured increase in tensile strength of CFRP. These results suggest that the matrices which show high yield stress or high failure strain in micro-scaled resin fiber tensile testing work to improve tensile strength of CFRP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Several studies have focused on the role of matrix resin properties on the tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP [1-4]. Behzadi, Foreman et al. have reported that yielding behavior (elasto-plasticity) of matrix resin strongly effects tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP. They determined yielding behaviour of matrix resin by resin compression test and the yielding behavior of matrix was introduced their finite element model of UD-composite They mentioned that the shear yielding of the matrix reduced the strain concentration factor in the fibres at the vicinity of a fibre fracture and

increased failure strain of composite compared to the elastic matrix model. Heuvel et al. investigated the influence of the matrix yield stress on stress recovery length and stress concentration factor experimentally by Raman spectroscopy. Three matrix systems differing in yield stress were used to prepare multi-fiber micro composite contained five fibers for Raman spectroscopy. Their results showed lower yield stress increase stress recovery length and slightly reduced stress concentration factor on adjacent fiber.

Therefore, understanding of yielding behavior (elasto-plasticity) of matrix resin is important to find out the correlation between matrix resin properties and tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP, and to determine proper resin properties to improve it.

The matrix resin that exists between fibers in CFRP can vary from submicron to micrometer scales. Matrix resin properties are generally evaluated using macroscopic specimens. This length scale is on the order of millimeters and can be orders of magnitude greater than that found in CFRP (microns). Therefore, the properties of the matrix at this length scale may deviate from the bulk epoxy properties. The specimen size effect on materials properties has been considered in a number of previous studies [5-7]. In general, strength of brittle network polymer, like epoxy resin, is governed by existence of defects, like micro-voids and micro-cracks. The probability of defects is strongly related to specimen volume, when specimen size is decreased, failure strain and strength is increased.

However, fewer studies have been reported on size effect of thermosetting resin on their properties. Odom et al. have studied size effects of epoxy resins using dog-bone tensile specimens with different gage volumes between 66~4590 mm³ [8]. Their results exhibited increases in failure stress as specimen size was reduced. However, the smallest specimen is still much larger than the matrix resin in CFRP because of machining limitation.

Hobbiebrunken et al. developed manufacturing method for epoxy fibers resin specimens with an average diameter of 40 μm, for tensile testing [9]. Their results indicate failure stress increased drastically as specimen volume reduced. Micro-scaled effect on failure stress has been reported in their study, but the effect on yield stress, stress-strain curve and failure strain is still unknown. Understanding of these properties is important to fully characterize the yielding and energy absorbing behavior of matrix resin. However, some voids were observed on their specimens and it adversely affected the failure stress, therefore developing a manufacturing method of micro scale specimen with minimal defects is necessary for accurate evaluation of micro scale mechanical properties of epoxy resin.

In this study, processing methods have been developed to produce high quality micro-scale epoxy fibers. Tensile test of these epoxy micro fibers were carried out to obtain elasto-plastic stress-strain behavior of epoxy resin. Evaluation of unidirectional tensile strength of CFRP composed of each epoxy resin systems were also carried out to understand the effect of matrix resin properties on CFRP tensile properties.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Materials

Figure 1 shows chemical compounds used for preparation of epoxy resin samples in this study. Diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA) was used as curing agent for all resin systems. All resin systems were formulated with 1:1 molar ratio of epoxide to active hydrogen of curing agent. Epoxy resin systems prepared in this study are listed in Table 1. Non-crimp unidirectional carbon fiber fabric (422g/m² of T700SC-24K-50C), was supplied by SAERTEX GmbH & Co.KG, and used to manufacture unidirectional CFRP panel for tensile test in this study.

Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane
(TGDDM, Araldite MY721,
Huntsman Advanced Materials)

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A
(DGEBA, Araldite GY6010,
Huntsman Advanced Materials)

Triglycidyl-m-aminophenol
(TGMAP, Araldite MY610,
Huntsman Advanced Materials)

Diethyltoluenediamine
(DETDA, Aradur 5200,
Huntsman Advanced Materials)

Figure 1. Epoxy compounds and curing agent used in this study

Table 1. Epoxy resin systems formulated in this study

Sample name	Epoxide blend	Curing agent
TGDDM	100% TGDDM	DETDA
DGEBA	100% DGEBA	DETDA
TGMAP	100% TGMAP	DETDA
TGDDM-A1	TGDDM with additive-epoxy compound α	DETDA
TGDDM-A2	TGDDM with additive-epoxy compound β	DETDA

2.2 Preparing process of epoxy micro fiber and macroscopic specimens

A small amount of formulated epoxy resin was poured into an aluminum cup and it was placed in oven at 130°C. After about 30-50 min, resin viscosity increased from about 0.01 Pa•s to about 10 Pa•s because of curing reaction. Epoxy fibers were created by inserting a needle of 500 μm diameter into the resin bath and extracting the needle to form resin fiber of approximately 50 mm in length. Fiber diameters in the range of 80 to 400 μm were created. The resin fibers were cut and attached on cardboard using high temperature tape, and cured at 80°C for 1hour and 130°C for 30 min and 180°C for 2 hour in oven. The specimens for tensile test were prepared according to standard test method for tensile strength and Young's modulus of fibers (ASTM C1557). Cured epoxy micro fibers were glued on cardboard with a 12.7 mm rectangular open window, defined as the gage length. The fiber ends are covered with additional cardboard on the frame to avoid crushing it by mechanical grips. Fiber diameter were measured at four equally spaced locations within the gage section by optical microscope and the average value was used as diameter of specimen in the data reduction. For precise evaluation of micro scale tensile properties, only specimens with less than 5 % variation in diameter with respect to the average value were used for tensile testing.

For manufacturing macroscopic epoxy resin specimens for tensile test, mixture of epoxy resin was poured into mold and cured at 130°C for 1 hour and cured at 180°C for 2 hour in oven, and the slab was obtained. The slab were machined to prepare dog-bone specimens with a gage length of 50.8 mm and a gage width of 12.7 mm and a thickness of 3.3 mm (According to ASTM D638 type 1).

2.3 Preparation process of unidirectional CFRP panel for tensile test

VaRTM technic was used to manufacture unidirectional CFRP panel with non-crimp unidirectional fabric as shown in Figure 2. Two plies of the fabric, which is cut 200 mm in width and 300 mm in flow direction, is placed between two layers of porous release film. Above the top layer of porous release film, a high permeability layer is introduced to aid the advancement of the flow along the face of the fabric. Resin injection was conducted at 80°C and curing was carried out at 130°C for 1 hour and at 180°C for 2 hour in oven. Volume fraction of fiber (V_f) was calculated as Eq. (1) The V_f were approximately 50% in all specimens.

$$V_f = FAW \times n / d \times t \times 10 \quad (1)$$

Where, FAW is the carbon fiber areal weight of non-crimp fabric (422g/m²), n is the number of laminated plies of non-crimp fabric, d is the density of carbon fiber (1.79g/cm³), t is the thickness (mm) of CFRP specimen.

Figure 2. Schematic of the VaRTM setup

2.4 Mechanical testing

2.4.1 Tensile test using micro scale epoxy fiber

Micro scale epoxy fiber tensile test was carried out with Instron Micro Tester 5848 with 5N load cell. A 1.27 mm/min (strain rate: 10%/min) crosshead speed was used. System compliance of tensile testing equipment was evaluated using stainless steel wire according to ASTM C1557, the value was calculated as 0.0178 mm/N. Engineering stress and strain was calculated as Eq.(2) and (3)

$$\sigma_e = F / A_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_e = (\Delta l - C_s F) / l_0 \quad (3)$$

Where, σ_e is the engineering stress, F is the applied force, A_0 is the original cross-sectional area, ε_e is the engineering strain, Δl is the recorded cross-head displacement, C_s is the system compliance, and l_0 is the gage length, respectively. Modulus were determined from the slope of the linear region of the engineering stress-strain curve. Energy absorption was calculated by integration of the stress-curve to the failure point.

2.4.2 Tensile test using macroscopic epoxy resin specimens

Macroscopic specimen tensile test was carried out according to ASTM D638. A 1.27 mm/min (strain rate: 2.5%/min) crosshead speed was used. Strain gage was used to evaluate engineering strain of macroscopic specimens. Engineering stress was calculated as Eq. (1) and modulus was determined

from the slope of the linear region of the engineering stress-strain curve. Energy absorption was calculated by integration of the stress-curve to the failure point.

2.4.3 Tensile test using unidirectional CFRP specimens

Unidirectional CFRP tensile test was carried out according to ASTM D3039. Specimens were prepared with a overall length of 250 mm and a tab length of 40 mm and a width of 12.7 mm and a thickness of 1.0 mm. A 1.27 mm/min (strain rate: 0.75%/min) crosshead speed was used. Strain gage was used to evaluate engineering strain. Engineering stress was calculated as Eq. (1), and modulus was determined from the slope of the linear region of the engineering stress-strain curve. Stress and modulus were normalized to V_f 60% value as Eq.(4) and Eq.(5).

$$\sigma_{60} = \sigma_e \times 60 / V_f \quad (4)$$

$$E_{60} = E \times 60 / V_f \quad (5)$$

Where, σ_{60} is the normalized value of stress, σ_e is the engineering stress, V_f is the volume fraction of fiber of specimen, E_{60} is the normalized value of modulus and E is the modulus.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tensile properties of micro-scaled epoxy fiber specimen

Tensile properties of micro scale epoxy fiber and macroscopic specimens were presented in Table 2. In this table, diameter range of epoxy micro fiber was limited to 100-150 μm for more precise evaluation. Epoxy micro fiber showed ductile behavior with distinct yield point in all resin systems as shown in Figure 3. In contrast, macroscopic specimens exhibited brittle behavior and a distinct yield point was not observed as indicated in Figure 4. Failure strain of epoxy micro fibers were significantly higher than that of macroscopic specimens with failure strain reaching 65% as maximum in DGEBA sample (about 10 times higher than the macroscopic specimen). In addition, yield stress of the fiber specimens (85-115MPa) were quite higher compare to maximum stress of macroscopic scale specimens (50-70MPa). We assume that the volume difference of specimens strongly affected their failure strain and strength.

Table 2. Tensile tests results using epoxy fiber specimens and macroscopic specimens

	Sample name	Yield Stress (MPa)		Failure Stress (MPa)		Failure Strain (%)		Modulus(GPa)		Energy Absorption (mJ/mm ³)	
		Avg.	SD.	Avg.	SD.	Avg.	SD.	Avg.	SD.	Avg.	SD.
Epoxy fiber specimen	TGDDM	103	6	107	10	25.1	10.8	3.13	0.23	2368	1142
	DGEBA	84	6	89	11	42.1	17.9	2.86	0.18	3328	1623
	TGMAP	106	5	112	10	21.7	14.5	3.40	0.30	2082	1550
	TGDDM-A1	99	6	114	24	29.4	21.6	3.01	0.20	2863	2517
	TGDDM-A2	114	6	107	5	20.3	9.1	3.35	0.16	1981	987
Macroscopic Specimen	TGDDM			51	5	1.7	0.2	3.60	0.09	46	11
	DGEBA			70	4	4.9	0.6	2.88	0.02	215	39
	TGMAP			70	16	2.3	0.8	4.30	0.35	97	55
	TGDDM-A1			63	14	2.6	0.9	3.37	0.04	97	61
	TGDDM-A2			60	19	1.7	0.7	4.29	0.22	62	44

Figure 3. Representative stress – strain curves of tensile tests using epoxy fiber specimens

Figure 4. Representative stress – strain curves of tensile tests using macroscopic specimens

3.2 Correlation of epoxy micro fiber properties to tensile strength of CFRP

The tensile test results of unidirectional CFRP were presented in Table 3 and the value of strength and modulus were normalized to 60% of fiber volume fraction. The average modulus of T700SC carbon fiber is 230 GPa. Based on the Rule of Mixtures, the axial modulus of the unidirectional CRFP with fiber volume fraction of 60% is approximately 138 GPa and is in excellent agreement with the results presented in Table 3 for all resins. The CFRP composed of TGDDM-A2 resin system which has the highest yield stress used in this study showed highest tensile strength. Heuvel et al. mentioned

that stress recovery length was decreased with increasing of yield stress of matrix resin [3]. It seems that this effect improved tensile strength of the CFRP composed of TGDDM-A2 resin system. Meanwhile, the CFRP composed of DGEBA resin system which has highest failure strain in this study showed second highest tensile strength of CFRP. Ganesh et al. have reported that the local strain of matrix resin around fiber breakage area is more than 20% in glass fiber/epoxy composite as shown in Fig. 5 [10]. The results imply that matrix in CFRP are also applied high strain locally around fiber breakage area, thus it is likely that high failure strain matrix like DGEBA system absorb more energy after fiber breakage and suppress generating matrix crack. It is believe that this effect reduce stress concentration factor on adjacent fiber and also enhance tensile strength of CFRP. These results imply that the matrices which show high yield stress or high failure strain in micro-scaled resin fiber tensile testing work to improve tensile strength of CFRP.

Table 3. Tensile test results of unidirectional CFRP

Sample name	Strength(MPa)		Failure strain (%)		Modulus (GPa)	
	Avg.	S.D.	Avg.	S.D.	Avg.	S.D.
TGDDM	2068	131	1.55	0.07	137	4
DGEBA	2304	60	1.67	0.06	138	2
TGMAP	2198	120	1.59	0.04	137	3
TGDDM-A1	2122	222	1.57	0.07	140	3
TGDDM-A2	2415	168	1.76	0.18	131	3

CF : T700SC-24K-50C non-crimp fabric

Strength and Modulus were normalized to 60% fiber volume fraction

Figure 5. Simulation results of axial strain that matrix applied around fiber breakage area at different yield stress of matrix
(Fiber diameter: 10 μ m, fiber Young's modulus: 90GPa, Vf: 50%, 2% applied strain)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, preparation method of micro scale epoxy fiber specimen for tensile test was developed to evaluate matrix resin mechanical properties at length scales representative of matrix resin in CFRP. Epoxy micro fiber showed ductile behavior with distinct yield point, while macroscopic specimens exhibited brittle behavior with no yield point observed. Failure strain of epoxy micro fiber was significantly higher than that of macroscopic specimens. In addition, epoxy micro fiber specimens showed quite high failure strength compare with macroscopic scale specimens. These results indicate that the tensile properties of epoxy matrix in CFRP differ significantly from the properties of macroscopic specimens.

Tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP was evaluated to verify the correlation with micro scale epoxy resin properties. The CFRP composed of matrices which showed high yield stress or high failure strain in micro-scaled resin fiber tensile testing exhibited higher tensile strength compare to others. The results imply that high yield stress matrices reduced stress recovery length and also high failure strain matrices reduced stress concentration on adjacent intact fibers after fiber breakage, both effect allowing for the measured increase in tensile strength of CFRP. These results suggest that the matrices which show high yield stress or high failure strain in micro-scaled resin fiber tensile testing work to improve tensile strength of CFRP.

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